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Investigating the addition of red beetroot (*Beta vulgaris* L.) in the improvement of nutritional and sensory properties of tomato paste

L. Hoxha^{1*}, M. Kullaj¹, A. Ismailaj¹, S. Ndoj¹, Ç. Kadakal²

¹Faculty of Biotechnology and Food, Agricultural University of Tirana, Tirana, Albania

²Faculty of Engineering, University of Pamukkale, Denizli, Turkey

*Corresponding author: lhoxha@ubt.edu.al

Abstract - Investigating different components extracted from fruits and vegetables can help to know their specific effect on many applications, like natural food additives. This study aims to investigate the role of *Beta vulgaris* L. in nutritional and sensory properties of tomato paste produced on a laboratory scale. With the purpose of exploring the effects of red beetroot application, were compared raw tomato (Tr) and red beetroot (Br), 100% tomato paste (TP100), red beetroot-tomato paste: 30:70 (TBP30), 50:50 (TBP50) and 100% red beetroot paste (BP100), and a commercial tomato paste product (TPc). Samples were evaluated for nutritional profile, colour values (L*, a*, b*), sensory properties, the total content of betalain, polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidant activity with two tests (DPPH and ABTS). Results showed that among protein, fat, carbohydrate, and ash content, no big differences existed. Fresh tomato and beetroot colour values L*, a*, b* resulted respectively, 41.46, 27.06, 23.56 and 25.79, 18.07, 7.82. After processing, an increase on L*, a*, b* values were noted in tomato paste mostly in samples TBP30 and TBP50. The betalain content in beetroot was 313.91 mg/100 g, and a loss of 6 % happened after processing in BP100, whereas in TBP30 and TBP50 its content was preserved in the amount of 25% and 87%. In fresh and processed tomato paste the content of polyphenols and flavonoids was 126 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g and 64.4 mg catechin equivalent/100 g, and antioxidant activity reached values of 43.02 and 91.6 as % of inhibition. The addition of red beetroot contributed to higher content of polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidant activity in tomato paste. The sensory properties, respectively colour and appearance resulted higher in TBP30, while aroma and texture resulted higher in BP100, for overall acceptability of the samples had the highest evaluation according to the trend: TBP30> BP100> TBP50> TP100. In conclusion the addition of red beetroot improved the nutritional and sensory properties of tomato paste, also manifested high stability and antioxidant activity, beside the colour enhancement. These findings suggest the application of red beetroot as a potential plant material in the formulations of tomato paste and as a functional additive beneficial to be used by the food industry.

Keywords - betalain, beetroot, nutritional profile, tomato paste, antioxidant potential, sensory properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fruits and vegetables contain many nutrients playing a significant part in the human diet (Choudhary et al. 2019; Esparza et al. 2020; Jiménez-Moreno et al. 2020), and they are rich in bioactive compounds. Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) is one of the most cultivated crops and its production worldwide exceed 100 million tons/year (Al-Harashsheh et al. 2009), consumed fresh or as processed into processed into tomato sauce, soup, paste, puree, juice, ketchup and salsa.

Beetroot (*Beta vulgaris* L.) has a world-wide distribution and its consumption is increasing steadily due to its recognition as an important source of essential compounds and natural antioxidants. Beetroot is utilized for manufacturing different food products and have been investigated by various researchers and food industries, due to prevailing effect of their color, flavor and nutritional aspect (Chhikara et al. 2018). Beetroot contains highly active pigments, betalains with plenty of health benefits, making them easily compatible with food fortification and supplementation (Zin et al. 2020; Jackman and Smith, 1996).

Betalains (E162), red-violet betacyanins and yellow betaxanthins, are used as natural colorants in food industries. They are water soluble nitrogen-containing vacuolar pigments present the in flowers and fruits of the most families of the Caryophyllales clade (Clement and Mabry, 1996; Herbach et al. 2006). With a high solubility in water, a wider range of pH stability (3-7, exhibiting yellow to red coloration), and the absence of toxicity (Herbach et al. 2006; Stintzing and Carle, 2004; Cai et al. 2003, Aberoumand, 2011). Interest in these molecules has grown since they possess anti-radical and antioxidative activities (Kanner et al. 2001; Pedreno and Escribano, 2000; Stintzing and Carle, 2004; Georgiev et al. 2010; Ninfali 2007; Pavlov et al. 2005; Pyo et al. 2004; Escribano et al. 1998). The aim of this study was to investigate the role of *Beta vulgaris* L. in nutritional and sensory properties of tomato paste produced on a laboratory scale.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The raw tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) and red beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) were obtained from local farmers in 2022, in Tirana, Albania. The samples after collection were labelled and immediately transported to the laboratory to continue further work with analysis and product processing.

Tomato paste was processed in laboratory scale, following the main steps: selected fully ripped tomatoes, washed and allowed to drain, pulped and screened from the skin and seeds, the pulp was concentrated in a stainless-steel pot (in atmospheric pressure), hot filled (82-88°C) into thermally processed air-tight containers, cooled, stored and stored at refrigeration till further analysis. Raw red beetroots, were separated from stems, washed, sliced and grounded in a blender. For red beetroot paste and their formulation with tomato (30% and 50%) preparation, the same scheme was followed. The samples were coded as follows: Tr (tomato, raw), Br (red beetroot, raw), and tomato paste products as: TP100 (100% tomato), TBP30 (70 % tomato and 30% red beetroot), TBP50 (50% tomato and 50% red beetroot), BP100 (100% red beetroot) and TPc (commercial tomato paste). Samples were evaluated for nutritional profile, colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*), and sensory characteristics. Total content of water, proteins, fat, carbohydrates, total sugars ash, total acidity (TA), were determined according to AOAC (2012), and the results were expressed as g/100 g in fresh weight of sample. pH was determined using a Bench-top pH meter Lab 865 (Xylem Inc., Germany). The colour value CIE (L^* , a^* , b^*) was determined by reflectance on two opposite sides of each sample using a portable colorimeter model NH310 (manufactured by Shenzhen ThreeNH Technology Co., Ltd., Shenzhen, China). For extract preparation, the procedure followed was according to Schliemann et al. (1999), with modifications. Samples were extracted with MeOH 80% (solid/solvent mass ratio was 1:10), solvent was slightly acidic, helping in stabilization of betacyanins and preventing the possible oxidation. The mixture was homogenized for 5 min in a vortex, treated for 15 min in ultrasound, and centrifugated (4500 rpm for 15 min). This procedure was repeated three times and supernatants were collected and filtered. The betalain content of methanolic extracts was determined spectrophotometrically (Silva et al. 2020), at a wavelength corresponding to the maximum absorption of each of the betalains, at 538 for betacyanins and 480 nm for betaxanthins, measuring the absorbance with the Libra S22 UV/Vis spectrophotometer (manufactured by Biochrom Ltd., Cambridge, UK). The content of betalains was estimated as the sum of both betacyanin and betaxanthin and the result expressed as mg per 100 grams of sample in fresh weight (f.w.). The total polyphenols content (TPC) was determined using Folin Ciocalteu's colorimetric method using gallic acid

as a standard, according to Singleton and Rossi's (1965) method with modification. The reaction took 60 min at room temperature in the dark, and the absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 765 nm with a Libra S22 spectrophotometer (Biochrom Ltd., Cambridge, UK). Results were expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 grams f.w. of sample. The total flavonoids content was measured by aluminium chloride colorimetric method according to Chang et al. (2002), with modification and using catechin as a standard. The absorbance was measured against reagent blank at 510 nm. The total flavonoid content was expressed as catechin equivalents (CE) mg/100 g f.w. of sample. The antioxidant activity with two tests, DPPH and ABTS the procedure was followed according to the method of Hoxha & Kongoli (2021), with modifications. A 15-member panel was used to evaluate the sensory characteristics of freshly prepared laboratory processed tomato paste. The panel was staff and students of Faculty of Biotechnology and Food, Agricultural University of Tirana, who were familiar with tomato paste quality. The panelists were asked to rate the tomato paste in terms of colour, aroma, texture, appearance and overall acceptability on a 9-point hedonic scale (1 = I do not like it at all, 2 = I do not like very much, 3 = Dislike moderately, 4 = Dislike a little, 5 = Neither like nor dislike, 6 = Like a little, 7 = Like moderately, 8 = Like a lot, and 9 = I really like it), adapted according to Meilgaard et al. (2007). Data for all parameters were reported as means of 15 judgments.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The quality parameters for raw tomato (Tr), red beetroot (Br), 100% tomato paste (TP100), red beetroot-tomato paste: 30:70 (TBP30), 50:50 (TBP50), 100% red beetroot paste (BP100), and a commercial tomato paste product (TPc), are introduced in Table 1. Results showed that comparing Tr with TP100 a decrease in moisture content (~20%) occurred as expected due to evaporation, and consequently an increase in the content of protein (2.7-fold), fat (1.6-fold), carbohydrate and sugars (till 3-fold), ash (4-fold), total acidity (1.4-fold). The commercial tomato paste had different parameters except the fat content compared to TP100 respectively the protein was higher (1.5-fold), carbohydrates and sugars were higher (~1.7-fold), ash was lower (5%), total acidity was higher (3-fold) and a lower pH (25%). From comparison of raw tomato and raw red beetroot it was noted that Br had lower moisture content (~5%), higher protein content (2.3-fold), lower fat content (~66%), higher carbohydrate and sugars content (~1.4-fold), higher values of ash (~4-fold), a very low total acidity and higher pH (1.4-fold).

Table 1. Nutritional profile of raw tomato, raw red beetroot and their processed products (mean values \pm SD, expressed g/100 g f.w. of sample)

Sample	moisture	protein	fat	carbohydrates	total sugars	ash	total acidity	pH
Tr	94.6 \pm 1.05	0.46 \pm 0.07	0.3 \pm 0.01	5 \pm 0.1	3.9 \pm 0.2	0.44 \pm 0.01	0.44 \pm 0.1	4.5 \pm 0.04
TP100	80 \pm 0.9	1.28 \pm 0.03	0.5 \pm 0.05	16.3 \pm 0.19	6.11 \pm 0.09	1.97 \pm 0.02	0.64 \pm 0.01	3.9 \pm 0.1
TPc	88.2 \pm 1.2	0.83 \pm 0.03	0.5 \pm 0.05	8.9 \pm 0.16	3.5 \pm 0.15	2.07 \pm 0.03	0.19 \pm 0.002	5.2 \pm 0.01
Br	90 \pm 0.7	1.09 \pm 0.02	0.1 \pm 0.01	7.13 \pm 0.12	6.1 \pm 0.3	1.74 \pm 0.2	0.05 \pm 0.001	6.4 \pm 0.02
BP100	78.2 \pm 0.6	1.36 \pm 0.02	0.1 \pm 0.01	19.1 \pm 0.42	8.14 \pm 0.28	2.03 \pm 0.03	0.06 \pm 0.001	6.2 \pm 0.04
TBP50	78.4 \pm 0.9	1.31 \pm 0.02	0.15 \pm 0.04	18.9 \pm 0.2	7.9 \pm 0.2	1.99 \pm 0.03	0.19 \pm 0.01	6.1 \pm 0.05
TBP30	79.4 \pm 0.75	1.29 \pm 0.01	0.39 \pm 0.03	17.8 \pm 0.1	6.8 \pm 0.1	1.98 \pm 0.03	0.32 \pm 0.2	4.8 \pm 0.02

When comparing Br with BP100, as in the case of raw tomato and its paste, due to processing a decrease in moisture content (~15%) happened and an increase in some components happened, such as protein (1.25-fold), carbohydrates and sugars (2.6 and 1.3-fold), ash (1.16-fold), while no differences were noted for total fat, total acidity and pH. Products TP100 and BP100 had slight differences among parameters, and was noted that addition of red beetroot (30% and 50%) caused slight increase in the content values of parameters, except in the total acidity, which resulted in a lower value, probably due to the contribution of red beetroot, which is characterised by a low acidity (0.05 g/ 100 g f.w.).

Figure 1. Colour values (L*, a*, b*) of raw tomato and red beetroot and their processed products

The total colour (Figure 1.) of the samples was expressed with CIE parameters L*, a*, b*, which resulted in positive values, respectively 41.46, 27.06, 23.56 (in raw tomato) and 25.79, 18.07, 7.82 (in raw red beetroot). After processing, an increase in L*, a*, b* values were noted in tomato paste, products. The brightness represented with L* values, ranged from 21.3 (BP100) to 43.26 (TP100); a* value, the red colour

was higher in laboratory processed tomato paste 35.87 (TP100) and lower in commercial product 8.65 (TPc); b* value, yellow colour was higher in tomato paste 31.82 (TP100) and lower in red beetroot paste 3.04 (BP100), which might indicate the presence of lycopene in Tr, TP100 and TBP30. The differences among laboratory made tomato paste and the commercial products could be due to the influence of the production method, and generally, our results were in good agreement with those reported by Kelebek et al. (2017), Sahlin et al. (2004) and Apuhan (2012).

Figure 2. Betalain content in raw tomato and red beetroot and their processed products

The betalain content (Figure 2.), which was calculated as the sum of betaxanthins and betacyanins reached up to 314 mg/100g f.w., and was not detected in Tr, TP100 and TPc samples. The addition of red beetroot in the tomato paste formulations contributed in the red colour enhancement (Figure 1.). Colour is an important quality attribute of food, and today's consumers have a distinct shift towards natural colours (Altinoz & Toptan, 2003), so betalain from red beetroot would be suggested to be utilized as a natural

colorant in the tomato paste. Furthermore, from the results was noted that beside the quantity of red beetroot added in formulations, the pH and temperature could be the factors influencing the stability of betalain during tomato paste processing. Related to the pH influence, in the case of tomato paste which resulted an acidic product (pH=3.9), had a positive effect on betalains stability in the formulations TBP30 and TBP50, as its content was preserved 25-87%.

Figure 3. The total polyphenols, flavonoid and total antioxidant activity in raw tomato and red beetroot and their processed products

The application of betalain in food products with a pH below 3, shift towards violet colour and above pH 7, towards blue colour (Wootton-beard et al. 2011). The thermal treatment affected the betalains stability during paste processing, and was noted a 6 % degradation of betalains (in BP100 sample). The raw red beetroot had the content of polyphenols 126 mg GAE/100 g, flavonoids 64.4 mg CE/100 g, and antioxidant activity 43.02% to 91.64 %, and these results we found that agrees with the study of Fidelis et al. (2017). By comparison of raw red beetroot (Br) with raw tomato (Tr) was noted to have higher content of polyphenols (2.47-fold), flavonoids (9.74-fold), and antioxidant activity (6.7-fold with DPPH test and 4.13-fold with ABTS test).

Figure 4. Sensory properties of tomato and red beetroot processed products

In the Figure 4., are presented the sensory properties of processed products, respectively colour (6.67-8.47), aroma (6.67-7.60), texture (6.87-8.40), appearance (6.40-8.53) and overall acceptability (7.20-8.53). The colour and appearance of tomato paste treated with 30% red beetroot resulted with higher value (8.47 and 8.53), while aroma and texture resulted higher at BP100 (7.60 and 8.40), compared to TP100 and TBP50. In terms of overall acceptability the samples had the highest evaluation according to the trend: TBP30> BP100> TBP50> TP100.

The different amount red beetroot added in the formulations of tomato paste caused differences in the antioxidant activity, which may be attributed to the betalains beside the total polyphenols and flavonoids content. This positive correlation observed confirm the beneficial use of betalains as natural antioxidants. Moreover, by comparison of TP100 with TBP30 and TBP50, would be noted that the addition of red beetroot contributed in higher content of polyphenols (3.7 to 6.4-fold); flavonoids (5.3 to 12.5-fold); and consequently, the antioxidant activity resulted higher (5.25 to 7.14-fold according to DPPH test, and 3.52 to 5.81-fold according to ABTS test). Thermal processing influenced the degradation of polyphenols in 64% and 2 %; of flavonoids 27% and 5%; and antioxidant activity 29% and 14% (DPPH test), 36% and 3% (ABTS test), from comparison of Tr with TP100, and Br with BP100. It was noted that red beetroot is more resistant than tomato, based on the degradation values, and our findings agree with Ceclu and Oana-Viorela (2020) which reported that processed red beetroot manifested high stability and antioxidant activity.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the role of addition of *Beta vulgaris* L. in the quality of tomato paste, produced on a laboratory scale. The results showed clearly that the addition of beetroot in different formulations can improve the overall quality of tomato paste, by causing an increase in the content of nutritional parameters, and influenced in lowering of total acidity. The total colour expressed with CIE parameters L*, a*, b*, resulted in positive values, and increased more after processing into tomato paste. Generally, the laboratory processed tomato paste was brighter, reddish and with the presence of yellow colour. The differences among laboratory processed tomato paste and the commercial product could be due to the influence of the production method, and generally, our results were in good agreement with those reported by literature. Moreover, the addition of red beetroot in the tomato paste formulations had a positive effect on colour enhancement, due to the presence of betalains. Based on this finding, betalain would be suggested to be utilized as a natural colorant in the tomato paste, although more detailed

investigations are needed to evaluate the potential and functions as a natural colourant. Beside the quantity of red beetroot added in formulations, was noted that pH and temperature influence the stability of betalain during tomato paste processing. The laboratory processed tomato paste with a pH=3.9, had a positive effect on betalains stability in the formulations TBP30 and TBP50, by preserving its content >25%. Also, the thermal treatment affected the betalains stability during paste processing, as a degradation ~ 6 % was noted in betalains. Regarding to the total polyphenols, flavonoids and antioxidant activity, raw red beetroot had higher content compared to tomato, and consequently their respective products, while commercial product showed the lowest values among all samples. The addition of red beetroot contributed in higher content of polyphenols up to 6.4-fold, flavonoids up to 12.5-fold, and antioxidant activity up to 7.14-fold according to DPPH test, and up to 5.81-fold according to ABTS test. The different amount red beetroot added in the formulations of tomato paste caused differences in the antioxidant activity, which may be attributed to the betalains. Even though thermal treatment resulted in losses of polyphenols, flavonoids and antioxidant activity, red beetroot is more resistant in their retention compared to tomato. The addition of red beetroot in tomato paste had positively influenced the sensory properties based on scores, respectively for colour up to 8.47 (in TBP30), aroma up to 7.60 (in BP100), texture up to 8.40 (in BP100), appearance up to 8.53 (in TBP30), and regarding the overall acceptability the samples had the highest evaluation according to the trend: TBP30> BP100> TBP50> TP100. The addition of red beetroot improved the nutritional and sensory properties of tomato paste, also manifested high stability and antioxidant activity, beside the colour enhancement. These findings would suggest application of red beetroot as a potential plant material in the formulations of tomato paste and as a functional additive beneficial to be used by the food industry. Further investigation should be done for finding alternative ways in utilization of tomato and red beetroot by-products into value-added food products.

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